

BMF CP106: Nigerian Female Business Owners' Characteristics and Business Energy Sufficiency

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“Through the trials of life, Kingfisher gains a deep understanding of the world. Naturally, living in this world means understanding the ways of business.”

–In “Bird Village Economics,” [Wild Wise Weird](#) (2024)

1. Project description

1.1. Main objectives

The current study is conducted to examine the following research questions:

- How is female business ownership associated with the business's energy sufficiency, affordability, and reliability?
- Are the relationships between female business ownership and the business's energy sufficiency, affordability, and reliability conditional on the owner's age?
- Are the relationships between female business ownership and the business's energy sufficiency, affordability, and reliability conditional on the owner's experience?

Findings from this study are expected to contribute to promoting the eco-surplus culture and sustainable development [1].

1.2. Materials

The Granular Interaction Thinking Theory (GITT) will be employed for the conceptual development of this study, while the Bayesian Mindsponge Framework (BMF) analytics will be utilized for statistical analysis [2,3]. The dataset comprises responses from 1122 small and medium-sized enterprises in Nigeria [4]. Statistical analyses will be conducted using the bayesvl R package, which utilizes the Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) algorithm for estimation [5]. For the sake of research transparency and reducing research and reproducibility costs, we have stored all data and computer code on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/16400484>.

1.3. Main findings

The preliminary analysis indicates that businesses with female owners are less likely to afford electricity than those with male owners. While the owners' age alleviates the negative effect, their years of experience amplify it (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: The estimated posterior distributions

2. Collaboration procedure

Portal users should follow these steps to register to participate in this research project:

1. Create an account on the website (preferably using an institutional email).
2. Comment your name, affiliation, and your desired role in the project below this post.
3. Patiently wait for the formal agreement on the project from the AISDL mentor.

If you have further inquiries, please contact us at aisdl_team@mindsponge.info

If you have been invited to join the project by an AISDL member, you are still encouraged to follow the above formal steps.

All the resources for conducting and writing the research manuscript will be distributed upon project participation.

AISDL mentor for this project: **Minh-Hoang Nguyen.**

AISDL members who have joined this project: **Quan-Hoang Vuong, Viet-Phuong La.**

The research project strictly adheres to scientific integrity standards, including authorship rights and obligations, without incurring an economic burden at participants' expenses.

References

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[5] Vuong QH, La VP. (2025). Package 'bayesvl' version 1.0.0. <https://books.google.com/books/about?id=znleEQAAQBAJ>

[6] Vuong QH. (2024). *Wild Wise Weird*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/BOBG2NNHY6>

